

Intramolecular Kinetic Isotope Fractionation in the Decomposition of Calcium Carbonate by 47% Aqueous Hydrobromic Acid. Part I.

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Different samples of calcium carbonate have been decomposed by 47% aq. HBr at temperatures ranging from 25° to 62°. The intramolecular kinetic fractionation factor, α is calculated for CO₂-CO₃²⁻ system at these temperatures. α values of the different samples have been found to be constant at a particular temperature. With increase of temperature α decreases and for this variation of α with temperature an empirical equation has been suggested. The lower value of α in the decomposition of carbonates by HBr in comparison to H₃PO₄ has been attributed partly due to oxygen isotope exchange between H₂O and CO₂ and partly due to the formation of unsymmetrical transition state.

WHEN carbonates are decomposed by acids two third of the oxygen is liberated as CO₂ and one third is used up in the formation of water. Thus the distribution of oxygen between two compounds CO₂ and H₂O results in the fractionation of oxygen isotope. The isotopic fractionation between the two species CO₂ and CO₃²⁻ has been expressed in terms of isotopic fractionation factor α defined as,

$$\alpha = (O^{18}/O^{16})_{CO_2} / (O^{18}/O^{16})_{CO_3^{2-}}$$

In terms of δ , α is expressed as,

$$\alpha = \frac{1 + \delta CO_2 / 1000}{1 + \delta CO_3^{2-} / 1000}$$

where

$$\delta = \left[\frac{(O^{18}/O^{16})_{sample}}{(O^{18}/O^{16})_{standard}} - 1 \right] \times 1000$$

δCO_2 is directly determined by a mass spectrometer but for the δCO_3^{2-} knowledge of α is essential. The values of α for the decomposition of several carbonates by phosphoric acid has been determined by Sharma and Clayton¹ at 25° and by Sharma and Sharma² and Pandey and Sharma³ at other temperatures. Using these values one can calculate oxygen isotopic ratio in a carbonate sample by measuring O¹⁸/O¹⁶ ratio in carbon dioxide gas obtained from the carbonate.

Study on the suitability of different acids for the experimental determination of fractionation factor

was carried out by McCrea⁴. He has suggested 100% H₃PO₄ to be the most suitable acid. Other acids such as formic acid, 100% HClO₄, 98% H₂SO₄ and nitric acid were found unsuitable. He stated that HBr (47%) is the next best suitable acid. In order to have an idea of the effect of the medium on the isotopic fractionation in carbonate decomposition by acids, the study with HBr (47%) has been carried out in the present work at various temperatures in the range (25°-62°) with a view to examine the effect of variation of the nature of acid on the kinetic fractionation factor α .

Experimental

Different carbonate samples of calcium were decomposed first by using 100% H₃PO₄ at 25° and then by using 47% aq. HBr at 25°, 30°, 36°, 45°, 55° and 62°. The procedure followed for the decomposition of carbonates by 100% H₃PO₄ was that described in our previous communications⁵⁻⁷.

The procedure adopted for the decomposition of carbonates by 47% aq. HBr is as follows. The weighed amount of the sample was taken in the main tube of a reaction vessel and approximately 15 ml of 47% aq. HBr (BDH, A.R.) was taken in the side tube of the vessel. The reaction vessel was closed after greasing the joints and connected to the vacuum line for evacuation after taking care that the temperature of the vessel was low (ice temp.) to avoid the copious fumes from HBr. When air was removed and sufficient vacuum was obtained, the stopcock of the reaction vessel was closed and the reaction was allowed to take place for 1 hr in a thermostat controlled at $\pm 0.5^\circ$. After the reaction was over the carbondioxide was extracted for isotopic analyses

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on a 6"-60° RMS-19 double collecting isotope ratio mass spectrometer, designed after Nier⁸ and McKinney *et al.*⁹ in the Department of Chemistry, I.I.T., Kanpur. The δ values were corrected for valve mixing and C¹³ variation according to the equation given by Craig^{10,11}.

Table 1 shows δ values of CO₂ as well as the CO₂ yield when the samples were decomposed by 100% H₃PO₄ at 25°. The carbon dioxide yield and δO^{18} values of carbon dioxide obtained by decomposition with 47% HBr at 25°, 30°, 36°, 45°, 55° and 62° are given in Table 2. The expected value of CO₂ yield is 10 μ moles per mg. The CO₂ yield obtained by the decomposition of both acids shows that all the samples of calcium carbonate have more than 99% purity.

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ISOTOPIC ANALYSIS OF CO₂ OBTAINED BY USING 100% H₃PO₄ ACID AT 25°

CaCO ₃ samples	CO ₂ yield in μ moles/mg	δO^{18}
CA ₁	9.95	-10.32 ± 0.02
CA ₂	9.94	- 9.36 ± 0.03
CA ₃	9.93	- 3.02 ± 0.02
CA ₄	9.94	- 0.76 ± 0.02
CA ₅	9.98	+ 1.10 ± 0.02
CA ₆	9.90	+ 4.65 ± 0.01
CA ₇	9.90	+ 7.66 ± 0.03

± = Average deviation for three analyses.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF ISOTOPIC ANALYSIS OF CO₂ OBTAINED BY USING 47% A.Q. HBR.

Sample of CaCO ₃	CO ₂ yield in μ moles/mg	Mean δO^{18}					
		25°	30°	36°	45°	55°	62°
CA ₁	9.96	-11.90 ± .02	-12.02 ± .03	-12.21 ± .02	-12.50 ± .02	-12.65 ± .02	-12.84 ± .01
CA ₂	9.93	-10.95 ± .02	-11.08 ± .02	-11.23 ± .01	-11.44 ± .01	-11.74 ± .01	-11.95 ± .01
CA ₃	9.93	- 4.63 ± .04	- 4.80 ± .03	- 4.97 ± .01	- 5.24 ± .02	- 5.51 ± .01	- 5.68 ± .03
CA ₄	9.95	- 2.43 ± .01	- 2.58 ± .01	- 2.72 ± .02	- 2.96 ± .01	- 3.26 ± .01	- 3.43 ± .02
CA ₅	9.98	- 0.62 ± .01	- 0.76 ± .01	- 0.92 ± 0.1	- 1.15 ± .01	- 1.39 ± .01	- 1.60 ± .02
CA ₆	9.92	+ 2.94 ± .01	+ 2.79 ± .01	+ 2.65 ± .01	+ 2.34 ± .01	+ 2.07 ± .02	+ 2.00 ± .03
CA ₇	9.92	+ 5.95 ± .02	+ 5.81 ± .02	+ 5.53 ± .01	+ 5.10 ± .01	+ 4.84 ± .02	+ 4.63 ± .03

± = Average deviation for three analyses.

Discussion

In the decomposition of carbonates by acids, fractionation of oxygen isotopes is caused due to the difference in the rates of decomposition of C-O¹⁶ and C-O¹⁸ bonds. Although the rate involves a time coordinate, but at infinite time, α approaches a constant value as discussed below.

The different carbonate species containing oxygen isotopes are CO₃¹⁶⁻, CO₃^{16O18-}, CO¹⁶O₂¹⁸⁻ and CO₃¹⁸⁻. Due to the low abundance of O¹⁸, the latter two species will be negligible. Therefore the carbonate sample may be considered to contain CO₃¹⁶⁻ and CO₂^{16O18-}

only, and hence the decomposition by an acid may be represented by the following equations.

Assuming M₁⁰ and M₂⁰ be the mole fractions of CO₃¹⁶⁻ and CO₂^{16O18-}, the O¹⁸/O¹⁶ in CO₂ gas at infinite time can be calculated according to Lindsay^{12,13} as

$$(O^{18}/O^{16})_{CO_2} = \frac{[k_1/(k_1+k_2)]M_2^0}{M_1^0 + [k_2/(k_1+k_2)]M_2^0}$$

Using the approach of Stacey *et al.*¹⁴, and assuming, β to be the atom fraction of O¹⁸, M₁⁰ = (1- β)³ and M₂⁰ = 3 β (1- β)². On substitution of M₁⁰ and M₂⁰ the equation reduces to :

$$\begin{aligned}
 (O^{18}/O^{16})_{CO_2} &= \frac{[3k_1\beta/(k_1+k_2)](1-\beta)^2}{(1-\beta)^3 + [3k_2\beta/(k_1+k_2)](1-\beta)^2} \\
 &= \frac{3k_1}{k_1+k_2} \times \frac{\beta}{1-\beta} \\
 &= \left[\frac{3k_1}{(k_1+k_2)} \right] (O^{18}/O^{16})_{CO_3^{16-}} \text{ since } \beta \ll 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

or

$$\frac{(O^{18}/O^{16})_{CO_2}}{(O^{18}/O^{16})_{CO_3^{16-}}} = \frac{3k_1}{k_1+k_2} = \alpha.$$

Here α is independent of k₀ and involves k₁ and k₂ only which is a characteristic property of intramolecular kinetic isotope effect. It depends on the relative rates of decomposition of light and heavy isotopes present in the same molecule. Therefore, it is evident that the different samples will have the same α values at a particular temperature. Table 4 shows the values of α calculated from δCO_3^{16-} and δCO_2

from Tables 1 and 2 respectively at different temperatures. The α value of each sample at a particular temperature is almost constant which is in agreement with the theoretical prediction. The errors in measurement are not affecting the constancy of α values appreciably as the deviations in α values due to the limits of the errors are in the fifth place of decimal.

For the evaluation of fractionation factor α in the decomposition of carbonates by any acid, knowledge of both δCO_2 and δCO_3^- is required. In the present work δCO_3^- has been indirectly determined by measuring δCO_2 for the CO_2 obtained from carbonates by decomposing with 100% H_3PO_4 at 25° for which α values are reported in the literature¹²³. Table 3 shows the values of δCO_3^- thus calculated and Table 4 gives the values of α , and mean $1000 \ln \alpha$ calculated for the different samples using 47% aq.HBr in the decomposition.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF δCO_3^- CALCULATED FROM δCO_2 OBTAINED BY 100% H_3PO_4 ACID METHOD AT 25°.

CaCO_3 samples	δCO_2	α'	δCO_3^-
CA ₁	-10.32	1.01008	-20.20
CA ₂	- 9.36	"	-19.25
CA ₃	- 3.02	"	-12.97
CA ₄	- 0.76	"	-10.73
CA ₅	+ 1.10	"	- 8.89
CA ₆	+ 4.65	"	- 5.38
CA ₇	+ 7.66	"	- 2.40

observed by the present authors. This can be attributed partly to the exchange of oxygen between

H_2O and CO_2 and partly due to the formation of unsymmetrical transition state.

The possibility of oxygen isotope exchange in case of 100% H_3PO_4 is negligible as shown by McCrea⁴. However, the possibility of exchange between water and carbon dioxide in case of decomposition by 47% aq.HBr can not be ruled out, and hence the lowering of α values may be due to the following exchange reaction :

TABLE 4—VALUES OF α AND MEAN $1000 \ln \alpha$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES USING 47% AQ. HBr. FOR THE DECOMPOSITION OF THE SAMPLES

CaCO_3 samples	α values at different temperatures					
	25°	30°	36°	45°	55°	62°
CA ₁	1.00847	1.00834	1.00815	1.00785	1.00770	1.00751
CA ₂	1.00846	1.00833	1.00817	1.00796	1.00765	1.00744
CA ₃	1.00840	1.00827	1.00809	1.00783	1.00755	1.00738
CA ₄	1.00839	1.00823	1.00809	1.00785	1.00755	1.00737
CA ₅	1.00834	1.00820	1.00804	1.00780	1.00756	1.00735
CA ₆	1.00836	1.00821	1.00807	1.00776	1.00749	1.00741
CA ₇	1.00837	1.00822	1.00794	1.00751	1.00723	1.00704
Mean $1000 \ln \alpha$	7.99	7.86	7.69	7.42	7.17	7.00

On plotting $1000 \ln \alpha$ against $1/T$ a straight line is obtained (Fig. 1) suggesting an empirical equation,

$$1000 \ln \alpha_{\text{HBr}} = \frac{2.67 \times 10^3}{T} - 0.97$$

for the variation of fractionation factor with temperature. A similar linear relationship has been observed by Sharma and Sharma² in case of decomposition of carbonates by 100% H_3PO_4 , but their value of $\alpha_{\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4}$ is higher than α_{HBr} values

The lowering of α values can also be explained on the basis of the difference in model of transition state. Assuming that two molecules of HBr attack simultaneously on the carbonate, the transition state becomes highly unsymmetrical, while the transition state by the attack of single molecule of H_3PO_4 as suggested by Sharma and Sharma¹⁵ remains symmetrical. According to Bigeleisen¹⁶ one expects lower isotope effect and hence lower fractionation factor in case of three centre reaction when the transition state is unsymmetrical. Therefore this interpretation

of lowering of the kinetic fractionation factor obtained in case of HBr is in accordance with Bigeleisen's prediction.

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